

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

TA'LIM - MUVAFFAQIYAT ESHIGI

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Kalit so'zlar: sifat, ta'lim, bolalar, usullar, stavka, adolat, o'qituvchi, jamoalar, vakolat, ahamiyat, asos, qashshoqlik, jamiyat.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda malakali ta'limning ahamiyati va ilg'or davlatlar amaliyotidan unga erishish usullarini ochib beradi. Ta'lim qashshoqlikdan qutulish va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy harakatchanlikni oshirishning kalitidir. Ta'lim tengsizliklarni kamaytirish va gender tengligiga erishish, shuningdek bag'rikenglik va yanada tinch jamiyatni rag'batlantirishga yordam beradi

EDUCATION IS THE GATEWAY TO SUCCESS

Key words: quality, education, children, methods, rate, fairness, teacher, communities, empower, importance, foundation, poverty, society

Abstract: This article discloses importance of qualified education in developing countries and methods to achieve it from practice of progressive states. Education is a key to escaping poverty and enabling upward socioeconomic mobility. Education aids in the reduction of inequities and the attainment of gender equality, as well as the promotion of tolerance and a more peaceful society.

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ — ПУТЬ К УСПЕХУ

Ключевые слова: качество, образование, дети, методы, скорость, справедливость, учитель, сообщества, полномочия, важность, основа, бедность, общество.

Аннотация: В статье раскрывается важность качественного образования в развивающихся странах и методы его достижения из практики прогрессивных государств. Образование является ключом к избавлению от бедности и обеспечению восходящей социально-экономической мобильности. Образование способствует сокращению неравенства и достижению гендерного равенства, а также пропаганде терпимости и созданию более мирного общества.

Whatever progress our society has made over the centuries is because of education. Being the foundation stone of society, education brings reforms, helps in progress and paves way for innovation. The importance of quality education cannot be undermined in a society, which is why [great personalities](#) have extensively written on its need in a civilized society. It is because of education, that humans have been able to explore the vastness of the universe and the mystery of its existence in atoms. The concepts like gravity, cognitive dissonance, laser-guided surgical procedures and millions of more would not exist if education were not there to unleash our potential. In the 21st century, some countries are lagging in the race for quality education.

The future sustainability goal that I would like to research in my publication is about quality education. I am going to focus on ways to provide more people with qualified education. Having the chance to be educated is every child's birthright. However, there are still lots of children who do have no access to qualified education. These children would become just ordinary people when they grow up even though they are talented in some areas. Unfortunately, there is still a dearth of talent in some areas. If we can figure out some ways that can provide more people with qualified education and make related policies based on them, we probably would find a flourishing in people qualified and want to work in those areas.

I am interested in this topic since I know some people who are talented in programming but did not have a chance to learn it when they were children. Before becoming programmers in their thirties, they taught themselves coding and programming after working as waiters and couriers for several years. These gifted people missed their chance of getting higher degrees in universities just because they did not have access to qualified education when in their childhood. The benefits of it are currently focused on children who are born in poor areas, but providing more children with qualified education can help our society get more qualified people for these positions and create wealth for the world. I hope there is

no lack of talented people in our community in the future. So, I think not only these poor children can benefit from these findings, but the whole society will definitely be paid off. Education is a key to escaping poverty and enabling upward socioeconomic mobility. Education aids in the reduction of inequities and the attainment of gender equality, as well as the promotion of tolerance and a more peaceful society. This is why the word “quality” is important. Schools and grades are key elements of an education. But if we’re investing time and resources into educating the next generation, we need some standard that can be used to measure how effective that education is.

The increasing number of crimes, wars, disease outbreaks, drastic economic downfalls, climate change, and many other factors have led to unexpected changes in societies around the globe. Due to this, the educationists and developmental organizations around the world emphasize the need for quality education and are stressing the need and uniting people towards achieving the goal. From educating a smaller group of people within their community to spreading awareness about the rising global issues, the educated people can work in an array of ways to achieve the goals. Besides formulating new methods, traditional methods like employing [drama and art in education](#) can also yield optimum results and help in enriching the educational process.

Some things that I already know about this topic is that in some poor areas, parents attach less importance to education. This phenomenon tells us if we want to solve this problem, we need to help these parents realize the importance of education and provide children chances to be educated at the same time. It is important to find ways to provide qualified education to children in poor areas and make their parents willing to send them to schools instead of pushing them to work and make money at a very young age. Besides, we also need to have some tests to figure out whether our methods work in these areas to adjust strategies and make them better.

The United Nations understand the supremacy of education for a brighter and prosperous future and is therefore of the consensus that quality education and not merely education should be a reality for all. In its Sustainable Development Goals, the UN has identified quality education as a major goal to ensure the ‘transformation of the world’ by 2030. By quality education, the UN implies equitable and standard education for all that will promote lifelong learning and the urge to gather knowledge. Inclusivity and equitability are the foundations to be upheld in quality education and not a greater literacy rate. This is a revolutionary approach to understanding education and making it the means of changing the world.

We all are aware of how [technology changing the face of education](#). Not only has the mode of receiving education changed but the methods of teaching students have also evolved. Earlier, education was more of a monologue, but nowadays, teachers encourage students to maintain a two-way flow of information in classrooms. United Nations has identified a multitude of problems at the global level that if not addressed can lead to serious problems. To tackle such issues, the need for leaders and experienced professionals who are adept in their respective fields has grown. To encourage leadership and power to influence among the students, it has become imperative to employ a refined way of teaching practices. In the age of technology, information can be accessed from anywhere in the world. Even though providing quality education demands great efforts to shape the personality of a student, with the advent of new technologies, a student is just a click away from requisite resources. While sitting hundreds of miles away from an educational institute, the students can take online classes from the institution, avail benefits of online career counselling, and access a great volume of resources from [free online libraries](#).

In 2020, Covid-19 hit the world and education was one of the most important factors that were adversely affected. A majority of countries announced

the temporary closure of schools impacting more than 91% of students in the world.

As per the UN, by April 2020, approximately 1.6 billion students were out of school and nearly 369 million children depend upon school meals. To ensure that education doesn't stop at this time, UNESCO has created the following aims:

- Help countries mobilize resources and implement new and context-appropriate solutions to offer remote education by leveraging hi-tech, low-tech and no-tech methods
- Seek equitable solutions and universal access
- Make sure that there are coordinated responses that avoid overlapping efforts
- Facilitate the return of students to school when they reopen to avoid an increase in dropout rates

Here are some of the details about quality education that you must learn:

- Before the pandemic, projections showed that more than 200 million students would be out of school and only 60% of young people will reach upper secondary education in 2030
- More than half of the students that have not enrolled in school live in Sub-Saharan Africa
- 617 million youth worldwide lack basic mathematics and literacy skills
- In 10 low and middle-income countries, children with disabilities were 19% less likely to achieve minimum proficiency in reading

Everyone can participate in their ways to provide quality education around the world. Here are some of the targets that the UN has set for 2030 in this section:

- By 2030, ensure that there is free primary and secondary education for girls and boys for effective learning outcomes
- By 2030, ensure that both girls and boys have access to quality early development development and pre-primary education

- Ensure equal access to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education

- Increase the number of people, both youth and adults who have relevant skills for employment, jobs and entrepreneurship

- Eliminate all discrimination in education
- Ensure universal literacy and numeracy
- Ensure education for sustainable development and global citizenship
- Ensure building and upgrading inclusive and safe schools
- Expand higher education scholarships for developing countries
- Increase the supply of qualified teachers in developing countries

Here is how you can promote quality education around the world:

- Find a charity that works for quality education, donate or get involved in other ways

- Donate the books that you have used to those who need it
- Promote and take free online courses
- Visit local schools, see what school supplies they need and start a

drive to provide it to them

- Mentor young children and help them with their homework or projects

Here are some of the important dimensions of quality education that every organization should meet:

- Equity
- Sustainability
- Contextualisation and Relevance
- Balanced Approach
- Child-friendly Teaching and Learning
- Learning Outcomes

A good teacher should have several qualities and some of them are:

- A good teacher should be a good communicator and must know not only how to communicate with the students but also with the other teachers and

school authorities especially when it comes to sharing the problems of the students as well.

- A good teacher is a good listener and must know to listen to the students and know their needs
- Adaptability is a crucial value of a good teacher, especially in these times as schools are moving online
- Good teachers are empathetic and patient with their students and understand what they are feeling and need.

Quality education is supported by three main pillars: availability to qualified teachers, the utilisation of quality learning resources and professional development, and the creation of safe and supportive learning environments. Quality education lays the groundwork for societal fairness. One of the most basic public services is high-quality education. It not only informs but also empowers residents, allowing them to participate as much as possible in their communities' social and economic growth.

Here are the three things that are required to provide high-quality education:

1. Study the content at your leisure at home, according to your learning needs.
2. Regroup in the classroom for hands-on workshops and conversations. Students are mentored by teachers.
3. With all of the insights from their class/group conversations, you may expand your knowledge at home.

REFERENCES

- [1].<https://leverageedu.com/blog/quality-education/>
- [2].<https://academicpartnerships.uta.edu/>
- [3].<https://www.concernusa.org/>